

Mg II chromospheric line asymmetries in Hyi

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Abstract

HD 2151 is considered the distant future of the solar evolution, with an effective temperature of 5852 K and surface gravity of $\log g=3.9$, it is classified as G2 IV. Here I present a brief analysis of the Mg II (h+k) chromospheric emission lines of HD 2151, from 126 stellar spectra taken from the International Ultraviolet Explorer database, recorded from 1978 to 1995. By means of a Lomb Scargle periodogram, an activity cycle of 11.05 years was obtained and two sub cycles of the order of 4 years. Also, the Mg II emission line bisectors were calculated, showing not only long term variability, but also showing variations within the same day of observations. On the other hand, it was observed that the h line was stronger than the k, in agreement with previous works. Concerning the Mg II K line bisector, it is worth noting that the largest dispersion value was observed at the maximum Mg II emission flux, and a variability cycle of 200 days was obtained.

1 Introduction

HD2151 is a G2 IV star, with a surface gravity of 3.9 and an effective temperature of 5852 K according to Battistini et al. 2015. Since it is considered the distant future of the Sun, Dravins et al. (1993), it has been observed for long a period of time in order to study granulation, activity cycles, rotation, among other features. Since the main purpose of this work is to relate the chromospheric line bisectors with the (possible) activity cycle of the star, it is needed a continuous monitoring of such star. One of the largest available spectral library is the online database of the IUE.

2 Mg II Spectra

The sample consists of 126 spectra taken from the IUE online database, recorded from 1978 to 1995, by the LWR and LWP high resolution cameras. The spectra was analyzed by two different approaches.

The first, being the most used in order to obtain the activity cycle of a star: the measuring of the Mg II (h+k) integrated emission flux along a spectral window, see for example Dravins et al. (1993), Buccino & Mauas (2008).

The second approach is by means of line bisector, proposed by Gray (2005b). The asymmetries in absorption line spectra are a consequence of several physical phenomena giving rise within the photosphere of the star, Gray (2005a), for instance, turbulence, convection, granulation, line blending, also, it can be considered as a consequence of magnetic activity Dravins (1999).

In this sense, we propose to measure the line bisector of the chromospheric Mg II (h+k) emission line, in order to observe variability of the line shift generated.

Variability in photospheric line bisectors has been observed in the case of Betelgeuse, Gray (2008), in which the line bisectors are used as indicators of mass motions in the photosphere of the star. The Mg II emission line bisector might represent a different phenomena, since the

Figure 1: An example of the integrated emission flux centered at the Mg II k line, with a spectral window of approximately 2 Å.

emission line forms upper in the chromosphere, where the convection might not be as stronger or prominent as it is in the photosphere.

3 Results

3.1 Mg II emission flux

As mentioned above, the integrated emission flux over the line profile of Mg II (h+k) was obtained for each spectra available, see figure 1, the errors in the emission are the one calculated by Composite Simpson's rule of numerical integration, and is a function of $\Delta\lambda = 0.0446\text{Å}$.

Figure 2: Integrated emission flux of Mg II (h+k) in relation with time. The star symbol represents the average from several observations taken the same day.

Once the integrated emission flux is measured for each spectra, we can observe temporal variability, as can be seen in figure 2, where the star symbol indicates the average emission from several observations made within the same day.

Using a Lomb - Scargle periodogram to the Mg II integrated emission measures, a large period of 4036 days (11.05 years), is obtained, see figure 3. Along with two other sub cycles of 4.8 and 3.6 years, from which only the later is statistical significant.

Figure 3: Lomb - Scargle periodogram from the emission integrated flux, in which the larger period corresponds to 4036 days, is marked with the lowest p - value with the red dotted line. The other two peaks correspond to 4.8 and 3.6 years respectively.

3.2 Mg II line bisector

The line bisector was measured for each h and k line, see figure 4, observing slight variations with observations recorded in the same day. Since the line asymmetry is a consequence of mass motions and turbulence, we calculated a line shift in order to represent variations along time. The line shift corresponds to the difference between the wavelength at the top of the line profile, and the one at the base, both from the line bisector. Since the Mg II is selfabsorbed at the center of the line, the upper and

lower wavelengths were selected for each of the left and right side, despite the stronger line is the red side, which is used to obtain the line bisector. Lineshifts variations

Figure 4: Example of a line bisector for the Mg II k line.

are observed showing a large dispersion at the maximum and a the minimum emission, see figure 5 From the bare

Figure 5: Line shift obtained from the bisector. Upper: Mg II h line shift; middle Mg II k ; lower: Mg II integrated emission flux, for comparison

variability of the line shifts over time, it is not clear the variations follow particular cycle. In this sense, we applied a Lomb - Scargle periodogram to the line shifts of the Mg II h and k bisectors. From which, a cycle of 214.2 days was found for the Mg II k line shift. The Lomb - Scargle periodogram for the h line did not resulted in any statistical significant period.

Figure 6: Lomb - Scargle periodogram of the Mg II k line shifts.

4 Conclusions

The larger cycle corresponding to 4036 days, is in agreement what is found by Buccino & Mauas (2008), in which the same analysis was made with the same spectra as used in this work. On the other hand, we propose another way to analyze the emission lines and stellar activity by means of the lineshifts from the bisector. It is interesting that, from the later analysis we were able to obtain a cycle of less than a year, only for the Mg II k line, but not for the h line, it is still unclear why the Mg II h line don't exhibit such cycle.

References

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